

BUSINESS ANALYSIS OF BULDANA URBAN CO-OPERATIVE CREDIT SOCIETY WAREHOUSE IN WARDHAS

D Kohale*, S C Nagpure**, S V Warade***, P N Khadse****

* Master of Business Administration in Agri-Business Management, School of Agri-business Management, Nagpur.

** Associate Professor (CAS) and Deputy Chief Seed Production Officer, CDF, Wani-Rambhapur, Akola. *** Associate Professor (CAS), School of Agri-Business Management, Nagpur. **** PhD Scholar- Department of Economics and Sociology, Punjab Agriculture University Ludhiana, Punjab.

snehalkohale2018@gmail.com

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Abstract

This research project provides an in-depth business analysis of the Buldana Urban Co-Operative Credit Society Warehouse in Wardha, established in 2016-17 under the leadership of chairman Mr. Radheshyamji Chandak, with 72 members, the study focuses on estimating the profitability of the warehouse and identifying the key challenges faced by both the warehouse owner and the farmers using the facility. The research utilizes a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods to offer insights into the warehouse's operational status, cost structures and financial performance. It also examines the revenue drivers and overall profitability, providing a comprehensive analysis of the warehouse's economic viability. Additionally, the project sheds light on the various constraints experienced by farmers, such as storage issues and market price fluctuations, which influence their ability to maximize benefits from the warehouse services. It also details the challenges faced by the owner in managing the warehouse, offering valuable insights for entrepreneurs looking to enter the warehouse business. The findings underscore the profitability of the warehouse business model, emphasizing its role in ensuring the safe storage of commodities, creating employment, and providing credit facilities to farmers. The research contributes to the existing literature by offering a detailed analysis of the warehouse business dynamics and suggesting areas for further investigation to improve operational efficiency and existing challenges.

Key words- business analysis, Warehouse,**Introduction and Objectives**

The terms storage, godown and warehouse are often taken and used as synonymous. Storage denotes function while godown or warehouse is simply the form of storage. Warehousing is used to describe the business or trade of storage and its prime objective is to profit from storage. It is an important link in the chain of marketing. It serves place and time utility and add to the place value of goods. These also smoothen out fluctuations in the supply and demand, which are often influenced by natural and political events. Warehouses are scientifically designed storage structures that protect the quantity and quality of stored products. The product is protected against both quantitative and qualitative losses by using the necessary preservation methods. Warehouses meet the financial requirements of the person storing the product.

Warehousing is an economic activity and denotes a dynamic aspect of commercial storage. It provides for safe keeping of goods in an orderly manner at suitable locations for easy retrieval when required for use. Commodities and wares in the warehouses for safe custody and return on payment of warehousing charges. The central and state warehousing corporations accept only such commodities for storage that can be stored under the provisions of the warehousing corporations of the Warehousing Corporations Act, 1962 and notifications issued there under (Chibber, 1982).

This study aims at comprehensive business analysis of Buldana Urban Co-Operative Credit Society Warehouse, Wardha. It is capacity wise large warehouse as compared to other warehouses in city, with capacity of 5700 MT, hence it is selected purposively for the further study to know more about actual working and economics of warehouse business. The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To estimate profitability of selected warehouse.
2. To identify constraints faced by farmers and owner of selected warehouse.

Materials and Methods

The present investigation was conducted in Wardha district of Maharashtra during financial year 2023-24, Buldana Urban Co-Operative Credit Society was chosen on purpose since it was the only warehouse large in size and storing food grains with capacity of 5700 MT. The survey included 30 farmers. The respondent for the study was operationally defined as the farmers who use warehouse to store their commodities. The primary data were collected personally with the help

of Survey schedules; the interviews were conducted in farmer's fields or in their homes through face-to-face contact.

Tabular analysis:

The primary data and secondary data collected are presented in tabular form to facilitate easy comparison. The constraints faced by users and owner of selected warehouse, profile of different commodities stored, others are presented in the form of tabular analysis. It was summarized with the help of statistical tools like averages, per centages and Garrett ranking techniques to obtain meaningful results.

To estimate profitability of selected warehouse:

Profitability means whether the business is economically viable or not. It was calculated by estimating total revenue, fixed cost, variable cost, net profit and B: C ratio.

Fixed costs:

Fixed cost are the expenses that remain the same no matter how much a company produces, such as rent, property tax, insurance, and depreciation etc.

Rental value of land = $1/6$ Gross value-land revenue

$$\text{Depreciation on machineries} = \frac{\text{Purchased value} - \text{Salvage value}}{\text{Useful life}}$$

Variable costs:

Variable cost are any expenses that changes based on how much a company produces and sells, such as labour, utility expenses, commissions, and raw materials etc.

Total cost:

It includes fixed investment and expenses on daily operations.

Total cost = Fixed cost + Variable cost

Gross return:

Total revenue generated from rent received through stored commodity before any tax deduction.

Net profit:

It means profit received after deducting expenses on fixed and working capital.

Net profit = Gross return – Total cost

Benefit: Cost Ratio

It is the ratio of discounted cash in flows (project benefits) to the discounted cash out flows (project costs), which must be unity or more

for an enterprise to be considered worthwhile. The technique also ranks for selection. The minimum ratio required is 1:1. This ratio of 1:1 indicates the coverage of costs without any surplus benefits. But usually the ratio should be more than unity in order to provide some additional returns over the costs for clear division.

$$B:C \text{ Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross return}}{\text{Total expenses}}$$

Statistical Tool (Henry Garrett's ranking technique)

This technique is used to evaluate the most significant constraints faced by the respondent. As per this method, respondents have been asked to assign ranks for all factors and the outcomes of such ranking have been converted into score value with the help of the following formula:

$$\text{Per cent position} = \frac{100 (R_{ij} - 0.5)}{N_j}$$

Where,

R_{ij} = Rank given for the i th variable by j^{th} respondents.

N_j = Number of variables ranked by j^{th} respondents.

Results and Discussion

Cost of selected warehouse

Table 1: Cost incurred by selected warehouse (Figure in Rupees)

Particulars	Total cost	Percentage
Variable cost		
Skilled labor	2,40,000	23.29
Unskilled labor	2,20,000	21.35
Electricity	45,000	4.36
Drinking water	15,000	1.45
Pest control	11,055	1.07
Stationary	16,000	1.55
Insurance	3,04,173	29.52
Miscellaneous	12,000	1.16
License	5,000	0.48
Intrest on working capital	86,822	8.42
Tax	75,322	7.31
Total variable cost	10,30,372	100.00
Fixed cost		
Rental value of land	2,16,709	90.35
Depreciation on machineries and equipment's	1,340	0.55
Intrest on fixed capital @ 10 per cent	21,804	9.09
Total fixed cost	2,39,853	100.00
Total cost	12,70,225	100.00

Revenue generated from stored commodity:

Following table 2 shows the commodity wise revenue generated through storage rent received during year 2023-24. Different commodities were stored during the year, rent received from each commodity different from each other as time period and storage charges vary according to type of commodities stored.

The table 2 shows the revenue generated from the storage charges received during financial year 2023-24. Here total revenue generated from storage charges of outgoing stock was 6,92,064 Rs. Where Storage charges received for rice contribute highest i.e. 43.56 per cent followed

Following table 1 shows the cost incurred by warehouse to successfully run the warehouse business, it includes cost required for fixed capital like land, building, machineries and equipment's.

Also, it includes variable cost that is the cost required to mitigate day to day work requirements like employee's salary, labour charges, stationary, electricity bill, drinking water bill, license and other miscellaneous expenses. Fixed cost and variable cost together called as total cost required to mitigate warehouse requirements.

The table1 shows the total cost required by selected warehouse for completion of warehouse operations. Table 5 shows the total cost of 12,70,225 Rs. incurred by warehouse to mitigate warehouse requirements, out of this cost on working capital was 10,30,372 Rs.

In case of variable cost, highest cost required for insurance purpose it shares 29.52 per cent of variable cost followed by expenditure on skilled labour salary i.e. 23.29 per cent and unskilled labour salary i.e. 21.35 per cent. Lowest cost less than one per cent required for license purpose i.e.0.48 per cent.

Total fixed cost on fixed assets rental value of land, depreciation on machineries and equipment's were 2,39,853 Rs. Out of this rental value of land required more i.e. 90.35 per cent of total fixed cost while depreciation on machineries and equipment's required only 0.55 per cent of fixed cost.

by soybean 28.99 per cent, other commodities share less contribution in revenue.

It can be seen from the table 2 that, total revenue generated from remaining stock in warehouse storage was 10,60,123 Rs. In which soybean contribute highest i.e. 69.19 per cent followed by cotton bale, while the other commodities share less amount.

So, the total revenue generated from storage charges received from outgoing and remaining stock in selected warehouse for financial year 2023-24 was 17,52,187 Rs. it contributes to the profit for the year.

Table 2: Revenue generated through storage charges (figure in Rupees)

Sr.No.	Stored commodity	Outgoing stock (Bag)	Revenue received from outgoing stock	Remaining stock (Bag)	Revenue to be received from remaining stock
1.	Soybean	9072 (28.99)	1,88,864 (27.28)	23615 (56.50)	7,33,235 (69.16)
2.	Linseed	734 (2.34)	63,050 (9.11)	180 (0.43)	11,060 (1.04)
3.	Mustard	1850 (5.91)	25,900 (3.74)	220 (0.52)	13,860 (1.30)
4.	Cotton bale	1622 (5.18)	28,785 (4.15)	7573 (18.12)	1,62,678 (15.34)
5.	Rice	13632 (43.56)	2,72,640 (39.39)	5622 (13.45)	84330 (7.95)
6.	Sago	440 (1.40)	8,350 (1.20)	4580 (10.95)	54960 (5.18)
7.	pigeon pea	846 (2.70)	21,068 (3.04)	-	-
8.	Chickpea	2158 (6.89)	30,056 (4.34)	-	-
9.	Chickpea lentils	180 (0.57)	1200 (0.17)	-	-
10.	Cotton yarn	757 (2.41)	52,151 (7.53)	-	-
11.	Total	31,291 (100.00)	6,92,064 (100.00)	41790 (100.00)	10,60,123 (100.00)
Total revenue			17, 52,187		

Note: Parenthesis represent percentage of total

Profitability of selected warehouse:

To estimate the financial viability of the selected warehouse business profitability ratio were calculated i.e. B:C ratio, also the net profit was

calculated to ensure that the selected business is profitable one and its expenses does not exceeds revenue generated.

Table 3: Profitability of selected warehouse (Figure in Rupees)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Value
1	Total cost	12,70,225
2	Gross return	17,52,187
3	Net profit	4,81,961
4	Benefit: Cost ratio	1:1.38

From the above table 3 it was evident that, selected warehouse able to earn normal profit. Therefore, for assessing the economic viability of selected warehouse, annual profitability of the warehouse was calculated for financial year 2023-24. The above table3 shows the cost, revenue and profit gained during that particular year.

It could be seen that the total revenue generated through rent received from storage of commodities was 17,52,187, which is more than the expenditure on fixed and working capital. The Net Profit earned by

selected warehouse was 4,81,961 and the B:C ratio was 1:1.38 which clearly shows that the selected warehouse unit is a profitable business.

Constraints faced by the farmers while utilizing warehouse facility:

The farmers were asked to list down the problems in the proposed system of utilization of the warehousing facilities by farmers and each of the problem statement was ranked from 1 to 5 based on the importance of each factor by the farmers itself.

Garrett's Ranking Technique was employed to analyze the ranked data and is presented as follows.

Table 4: Constraints faced by farmers during storage in selected warehouse.

Constraints Preferences	Regulatory hurdles	High storage charges	Lack of credit facility	Transport-ation cost	Lack of labor availability
1 st	12	10	7	1	0

2 nd	9	11	5	3	2
3 rd	7	6	13	3	1
4 th	2	3	4	9	12
5 th	0	0	1	14	15

The table 4 shows the preference and ranking of constraints faced by the respondent farmers utilizing warehouse facilities. Among the 30 farmers regulatory hurdles ranked as first by 12 respondents, second ranked by 9 respondents. Similarly, high storage charges ranked as first by 10 respondents, second ranked by 11 respondents. In the same way all respondents gave ranking to constraints they faced. The Garrett's ranks were calculated by using appropriate Garrett's Ranking formula. The based on the Garrett's ranks, the Garrett's value was calculated. The

Garrett's tables and scores of problems listed in above table, and multiplied to records scores in table , finally by adding each row the total Garrett's score were obtained.

Calculating Per cent Position and Garrett score:

Following table shows the per cent position calculated using per cent position formula and from that Garrett's score were selected from Garrett's score table.

Table 5: Per cent Position and Garrett's score for constraints listed by farmers.

Rank	100 (Rij-0.5)/N	Per cent position	Garrett score
1	$100(1-0.5)/5$	10	75
2	$100(2-0.5)/5$	30	60
3	$100(3-0.5)/5$	50	50
4	$100(4-0.5)/5$	70	40
5	$100(5-0.5)/5$	90	24

From above table 5 is can be seen that Garrett's score for rank 1st were 75 ,for rank 2nd were 60, for 3rd rank were 50 ,for rank 4th was 40 and

for rank 5th it was 24 by using Garrett's score for each rank average calculated.

Table 6: Average of total score and rank assigned to the constraints

Particulars	Garrett's score					Average	Rank
	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th		
Regulatory hurdles	900	540	350	80	0	62.33	I
High storage charges	750	660	300	120	0	61.00	II
Lack of credit loan facility	525	300	650	160	24	55.30	III
Transportation cost	75	180	150	360	336	36.74	IV
Lack of labor availability	0	120	50	480	360	33.65	V

From the above table 6, the most important constraint that the farmers expect to arise from "utilization of warehousing facilities by farmers" is regulatory hurdles means when farmers wanted to store their commodities in warehouse, they have to follow some paperwork which became hectic process for them. Another major constraint was private warehouse charges more than government warehouses. They are assuming that they will get loan easily from any financial institution by using warehouse receipt but they can only use that receipt to get credit loan in "Buldana Urban Co-Operative Credit Society Bank" itself this is also a major concern of farmers.

Following these factors, the farmers have to abide the transportation cost from the field to the warehouses in the proposed system. But in case of the existing channel, the commission agents or the cooperative societies themselves take the produce from the field to the processing unit. Also lack of labour availability is a constraint faced by farmers as they have to take their own labour with them to load and unload their produce many times they find it difficult to get potential labour.

Constraints faced by owner of selected warehouse:

Following table shows the constraints faced by owner of warehouse business, owner was asked about the constraints they faced while running the warehouse business and assigned rank accordingly.

Table7: Constraints faced by owner of the selected warehouse

Sr.No.	Constraints	Rank
1.	Unavailability of skilled and unskilled labor	I
2.	Financial constraints	II
3.	Competition among warehouses	III
4.	Administrative problems	IV

5.	Less demand by users	V
6.	Maintenance problems	VI
7.	Risk of damage of commodities	VII

From above table7 it could be seen that, the major constraint is unavailability of skilled and unskilled labour for that he assigned first rank followed by financial constraints, competition among warehouses, administrative problems, less demand by users, maintenance problems and risk of damage of commodities.

Conclusion

1. It is revealed from the results that, the total revenue generated through rent received from storage of commodities is more than the expenditure on fixed and working capital. The Net profit earned by selected warehouse and the B:C ratio clearly shows that the selected warehouse unit is a profitable business.

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2. From the results obtained it conclude that, while utilizing warehouse facility the major constraints faced by farmers is, regulatory hurdles followed by high storage charges, lack of credit loan facility, transportation cost and lack of availability of labour.
3. It is concluded that, the major constraints faced by owner of selected warehouse were unavailability of skilled and unskilled labour for that he assigned first rank followed by financial constraints, competition among warehouses, administrative problems, less demand by users, maintenance problems and risk of damage of commodities.